

THE EFFECT OF POLITICAL COMMUNICATION, FIGURES IN POLITICAL PARTY, POLITICAL COSTS, GOVERNMENT SUPPORT FOR PUBLIC TRUST AND ITS IMPLICATIONS ON VOTING INTENTION

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Abstract

This study aimed to explore the effect of political communication, figures in political parties, political costs, and government support on public trust, which have implications for the intention to choose political parties. This research focuses on the voters of national and local political parties in Aceh using explanatory research and qualitative research models. Data were collected using a closed questionnaire with a 5-category Likert scale. Samples were collected using a proportional random technique, and data were analyzed using SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) analysis with the help of AMOS 22 software. The study's results prove that political communication, figures in political parties, political costs, and government support significantly affect public trust. Furthermore, public trust significantly affects the intention to choose a political party. Therefore, with the special conditions in Aceh, where local parties are more dominant than national parties, it is important to build political communication, figures in political parties, political costs, and good government support to increase public trust and affect the intention to vote for political parties.

Keywords: Political Communication, Political Costs, Government Support, Public Trust, and Voting Intention.

1. INTRODUCTION

The political system is a variety of activities and functions that work in a unit and entity in the form of a state or society. The political system is a pattern of public relations that is formed based on legitimate decisions within the community. Research on political marketing has now been done a lot. Politicians cite theories in the marketing of goods and services. However, some think that the marketing theory used in marketing goods and services may not be fully appropriate when applied in the political field. (Lees-Marshment et al., 2014) states that political marketing is an important topic in the academic study and practice of politics around the world. In general, voters are analogized as consumers, the political system as a market, policies as various products and services, and what is constantly being discussed are promises that can be fulfilled and the need to convey them to the government. This is considered a success in the selection process in a highly volatile and unpredictable market.

Peng & Hackley (2009) argue that there may be aspects of audience response to political advertising that are inconsistent with brand marketing theory. Voters and consumers appear to have similar affective, cognitive, and behavioral responses to advertising, as political parties and commercial entities sometimes use similar marketing techniques. However, voters display certain responses that set them apart from consumers. This implies that the analogy between commercial and political marketing has limitations. (Peng & Hackley, 2009) study suggests that the voter-consumer analogy makes much sense when viewed at the macro level but becomes weaker as the research focuses on individual micro-level analysis in elections. This difference of opinion makes research on political marketing important study suggests that the voter-consumer analogy makes much sense when viewed at the macro level but becomes weaker as the research focuses on individual micro-level analysis in elections. This difference of opinion makes research on political marketing important.

Political marketing is not only focused on how producers can sell products to consumers but also on how producers can attract consumers to buy or choose. Political marketing is needed to assist political contestants or political parties in building relationships with the public. The relationship that is made is what will then create a political market. The first and foremost thing that needs to be done in the political market is to encourage people's interest in voting decisions. In building public interest in voting, political contestants or political parties are required to reflect the best quality of work to form a good image in the people's minds. If political parties continuously build a positive image, the people's voice and sympathy will be able to be achieved. On the other hand, if political parties cannot create a positive image, the public will become antipathetic and reluctant to vote. This will have an impact on the number of votes that will decrease.

Political communication as political activity is the delivery of messages characterized by politics by political actors to the public or other parties. Communication that is carried out by maintaining good relations with the community, disclosure of information, and building trust need to be made by every cadre of political parties to get full support during the general election that will be held later. This activity is carried out in real life in social life and political communication when campaigning or otherwise. The political communication strategy developed by each party from the start was designed to achieve and gain full support in the general election. For political communication to run according to the expectation, there needs to be unity and good relations between the people in the political party.

A person's decision to take a certain action is generally preceded by an intention to perform that action. The intention is something that happens in a person's heart to do something in the future. A strong intention will encourage action, including the act of choosing a political party. Intention to vote in elections is determined by the subjective views of voters that lead to negative or positive voter attitudes. Judging from the definition of intention according to Fishbein and Ajzen (2010), the intention is a person's subjective view which is the beginning of the formation of behavior. The intention is not a behavior but is still at the cognitive level. This intention will still exist in a person, which will later come into behavior when the individual feels the opportunity and the right time.

Surbakti Ramlan (2018) conveyed that political participation shows the intention to choose two to be active participation and passive participation. Active participation in political parties is in the intention to propose a public policy, propose public policy alternatives made by the government, submit criticisms and improvements to policies, pay taxes, and elect government leaders. On the other hand, activities that are included in the passive participation category are activities that obey the government, accept, and carry out every government decision. Voters' intention to choose a particular party does not just happen but is determined by various things, including political communication, government support, and public trust (Cangara, 2009). Building a strong politics also makes a big investment in moving the masses and political promises that are programmed and become proof of the results of victory. According to the concept (McNair, 2011) that the allocation of public resources, official authorities, and official laws, are powerful financing as political communications. To see the causes of the phenomenon of a decrease in the number of seats in parliament from local parties and an increase in the votes of national parties which shows a trend at the party level indicating a significant decline in party votes. Then, the national party showing the increase in votes slowly began to rise again.

Associated with political costs Firmanzah, (2007) explained that the costs in political marketing include further economic, psychological, and national image costs. On the other hand Erdil & Özdemir, (2016) conveying political costs greatly affect voter response (intention to vote). Furthermore, this statement is consistent with (Maryani, 2015) and (Ahmed, 2015) (Community Empowerment-Dede Maryani, Ruth Roselin E. Nainggolan-Google Books, n.d.) political costs have a positive and significant role in winning a political party in increasingly fierce competition. Building a strong politics also makes a big investment in mobilizing the masses and political promises that are programmed as well as proving the results of victory.

According to the concept (McNair, 2011) that the allocation of public resources, official authority, and official laws, strong financing as political communication. To see the causes of the phenomenon of the decrease in the number of seats in parliament from local parties and the increase in the votes of national parties which show a trend at the party level, showing a significant decline in party votes. Then, the national party showing the increase in votes slowly began to rise again. In this case, the researcher has conducted interviews with nine practitioners and political party leaders in Aceh, the results are as summarized in the following Table 1:

Factors that caused the decline of local parties and the increase of national parties

No.	Causative factor	Description
1.	The national party in power in parliament is getting stronger	National parties such as the Gerindra, Nasdem, Democrat, and Golkar parties are gaining more and more seats in parliament
2.	The Aceh Party energy is getting weaker	Their internal division caused the Aceh Party officials to see the exit of Zaini Abdullah, Zakaria Saman because they actually had loyal supporters who were able to reduce the number of votes in the party.
3.	The electoral system that applies based on Law No. 7 of 2017 concerning Elections is designed to be carried out simultaneously	The Aceh Party faces demands that it must win the presidential candidate Prabowo, the presidential election wins its own party in the Pileg, and also wins its cadres who enter the national party. This caused his energy to be divided and not focused on the point of raising the Aceh Party itself or the national party.
4.	The militancy of the cadres, sympathizers of the Aceh Party management is less active in the field in terms of conveying the Development program and the results of the 2005 Helsinki Mou agreement. The Aceh Party is one of the local parties that is expected to be an agent of change to improve welfare, education, finance, as stated in the MoU agreement.	From some hopes that the fastest is felt, the Aceh Party did not win in the 2017 Pilkada which weakened the position of power. In addition, at the district/city level, many cadres lost in the 2017 Pilkada, including; Pidie, Bireun, Abdya, Banda Aceh, Aceh Besar, South Aceh, Aceh Tamiang.
5.	Lack of self-reflection to make positive changes for the Aceh Party itself	The current condition of the Aceh Party seems to have lost its spirit of struggle and direction in realizing the vision and mission that has been used as the foundation for the founding of the party
6.	Political promises made to constituents do not match the data and reality on the ground	Many political promises are not in line with people's expectations and show real commitments that have not been realized, causing a decline in trust in constituents.
7.	Proof is done by confirming with other political party figures the level of truth of the data	In testing the validity of the data, researchers can try to meet directly with political actors, to seek information about political conditions in Aceh

Source: Interview Results, processed (2020) From the results of the study, national parties in terms of organizational structure have a better cadre system, party consolidation internally and externally has formed organizations from the central, provincial, district/city, village and even branch (grassroots) levels. Another thing that is owned by national parties is that many administrators are highly educated and have broad insights in terms of party development and innovation according to organizational needs. On the other hand, what is no less important is the experience of being in an organization that already has long experience so that many presidential regimes from the beginning of independence have gone through various challenges and obstacles.

Another factor that affects the intention to vote is the government's support for public trust. The government support factor is reinforced by the statement (Russell Dalton, 2017) that government support is needed to strengthen the intention to vote for a party in the future. The same thing is also in line with the statement above, this study will insert government support (government support) as one of the factors that will be tested for its influence on the intention to vote for a party. Meanwhile, further studies state that government support alone is not enough to shape the intention to vote for a party (Robert, Roulin, 2015). Parties with strong government support will gain goodwill and understanding from the public in general, including internal stakeholders (Abugre, 2017:20). Furthermore, according to Brollo and Nannicini, (2009), the government's support will help the party to improve through institutional culture building in the form of discipline, motivation, service improvement and work productivity which are expected to create a sense of belonging to the party so that it has an impact on the strength of the party public trust (Abugre, 2017).

Furthermore, according to Miriam Budiarjo (2008) the basis of political science in general defines political participation or intention to vote as the activity of a person or group of people to actively participate in political life, namely by electing state leaders directly or indirectly influencing government policies. Besides that Roberts et al., (2003) states that political participation and intention to vote is the active involvement of individuals and groups in government processes that have an impact on life. This includes involvement in decision-making and oppositional action, the important thing is that participation is an active process, directed at influencing the running of the Indonesian People's Legislative Assembly and government so that political participation will affect life. Public trust, according to Choudhary, (2008), has several different terms that are often used to describe phenomena related to belief, such as confidence, reliability, and trustworthiness. The tendency to use terms that differ depending on the context is natural and occurs in many countries. This can happen because the concept of public trust is multidimensional and is the subject of various disciplines, such as psychology, sociology, politics, economics, and public administration.

Based on the conclusions on the findings in the field and several studies that the ability of political communication, political costs, and character in political parties or the ability of candidates and good public trust do not necessarily affect the trust and intention to vote. This study suspects that to increase the intention to vote for a political party, another factor is needed, namely government support. This study examines the effect of political communication, figures in political parties, political costs, government support on public trust, and intention to choose political parties. Political parties in Indonesia have developmental dynamics closely related to very diverse social conditions, so they are fascinating to study.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Political Communication

Political communication according to Michael Rush and Philip Althoff, (2012) is a process in which relevant political information is passed from one part to another, and between social systems and political systems. Cangara, (2009) explains that political communication is a

communication activity that is political in nature, has political consequences, or influences political behavior. Therefore, political communication meant by Cangara, (2009) can be characterized by political communicators, namely individuals who are in an institution, association, political party, mass media management institution, and public figure. This communication skill will provide an understanding of the party, generate movement, and create a harmonious relationship to create a propaganda effect and confidence in the audience.

The impact created by this political communication effort is establishing harmonious relations with the community through the existence of capable propaganda, as explained by Abugre, (2017). He stated that the occurrence of political communication with many directions would easily achieve political goals. Thus, the effect of this political communication will strengthen public trust better. In other words, the better the political communication activities, the better the trust. According to Cangara (2014), indicators in political communication include: (1) Political communicators, (2) Political messages, (3) Political channels or media, (4) Political goals or targets, and (5) Influence and effects of political communication.

2.2 Figure in Political Parties

According to Nursal quoted by Ali (2010) states that strong leadership or a figure in the party will shape the attitude of a voter towards that figure. So that they can determine their choice of political parties, this is because the leader as one of the party figures has a very close relationship with his party and is a benchmark of performance. So that the party's character is one of the factors that influence a person's attitude in the decision to choose a political party. Besides that, Peter (2007) describing character in a political party is a perception or emotion that is maintained in good condition by oneself and not others. According to Montoya (Haroen, 2014), there are eight indicators of personality in political parties (personal branding), including: (1) Specialization, that is, a great personality in a political party has the characteristic of proper specialization, and focusing only on one strength, expertise, or certain achievements, (2) Leadership, namely a leader who can become a decision maker in an atmosphere full of uncertainty, and is able to provide clear directions to meet public needs, (4) Personality, that is, a person is enough to be himself as he is, (5) The difference is to create an effective personal branding that can make it something that stands out and is easy to remember in people's minds, (6) Visible, that is, a person needs to continue to market himself in every chance/consistent, (7) Unity, namely moral ethics and attitudes must be in accordance with what has been determined, so that it will not lead to pretense in acting, (8) Firmness, namely a person must not hesitate or intend to change the form of personal branding that has been set from the start, and (9) Muhibah, namely someone who is perceived in a positive way and associated with a value or idea that is generally recognized as useful, will have a better personal branding impact and can last longer.

2.3 Political Costs

Watt and Zimmerman (Mills, et al., 2012) explained that political costs are budgets that are needed directly or indirectly to support the operational activities carried out by political participants in the legislature and regional heads, such as costs for administration, campaigns,

operational success teams, to witness operations at voting venues. Costs in political marketing cover many things, from economic, psychological to national image (Niffenegger, 2013).

According to Ikhsan and Shihab (2010) indicators of political costs can include three components, namely: (1) Cost of economic value is how to minimize risk, (2) Psychological costs are how to bring pride to the political area, (3) Image Nationalism is how voters feel the candidate can give a positive image and can be the pride of the country.

2.4 Government Support

In world government, there is political support which is very much needed from all aspects of political institutions in carrying out those related to democracy and state administration (international of public administration Norway 2011). This forms a good opinion so that this party will be liked by the people with the target audience or party stakeholders. Thus, parties with strong government support will gain goodwill and understanding from the public in general, including internal stakeholders (Abugre, 2017). This political communication effort can establish harmonious relations with the community through the existence of capable propaganda, as explained by Abugre, (2017). Thus, the effect of this political communication will strengthen the intention to vote for a better party. In other words, the better the political communication activities, the better the intention to vote. Basedau and Stoh (2008) collected various opinions which illustrate a partial understanding of the role of political parties and government support, focusing on capacity building on several indicators, as follows: (1) Stability in inter-party competition, (2) Parties with more stable roots, and (3) Party and government legitimacy. All of these capability enhancements were developed as a strategy to embody the values of “good governance”.

2.5 Public Trust

In public trust in political parties, it can be said to be the essence of the relationship between political parties and society. Political parties need support and trust from the public in carrying out their roles in the political system. Without the support and trust of the people, it is impossible for a political party to gain power and carry out all of its work programs. Hair and Mc Daniel (2012) Hair and Mc Daniel (2012) argue that public trust is an effort that is deliberately carried out, planned on an ongoing basis to create mutual understanding between an institution/institution is an art as well as a social science in analyzing trends, predict the consequences, provide direction to the leadership of the institution/institution and carry out planned programs that can meet the interests of both the institution and the institution and the community concerned.

Public trust in the perspective of economics views that trust tends to be seen from expectations that are calculative and rational for the results provided by an organization or other party (Kim, 2007; Williamson, 1993 dalam Dwiyanto, 2011). According to Maharani (2010) There are four indicators in the trust variable, namely: (1) Reliability to measure the consistency of a company in carrying out its business from the past to the present, (2) Honesty, namely how political party figures/marketers offer products or services that match the information provided by the company/marketers to their consumers, (3) Concern always serves constituents well and

accepts complaints that consumers complain about and always makes consumers a priority, (4) Credibility Quality or strength, namely parties or political institutions to increase consumer confidence in serving and protecting.

2.6 Intention to Choose

Basically, the intention to vote or the election made by consumers in the world of politics is not much different from the restoration of goods and services, the difference is only seen in the dominance of the candidate factor, so the statement appears from Bergman and Wickert (2011) “the man is the message” or “the leading candidate is the platform”. Voting intention is a tendency and desire that strongly encourages individuals to vote for a candidate (Bosnjak, et al., 2006). In the marketing concept in general, Amstrong and Kotler (2009) state "Consumer purchases are influence strongly by cultutal, social, personal, and psychological characteristic", Voting intention is a motivational factor that encourages individuals to choose a particular candidate, therefore purchase intention is the best method for predicting consumer buying behavior. Kotler (20011) states that there are five stages in the selection decision process, namely need recognition, information search, evaluation (assessment) of alternatives, purchasing decisions and post-purchase behavior.

3. METHODS

Based on the literature review and hypotheses, the research model can be presented in the following diagram:

Figure 1: Research Model

The population of this study is all registered voters in the final voter list, which totals 2,826,743 people (Aceh Independent Electoral Committee or KIP, 2020). Determining the number of samples refers to the opinion of Sekaran (2010) which states that for SEM analysis, the number of samples is at least 5 times the number of indicators, so the number of samples is 400 (55 x 5). Determination of the number of samples in each region (electoral district) using the Cochran formula.

Table 2: Population, Sample Area, and Number of Samples

Selected area by region		Number of voters	Sample area	Population of sample area	Number of samples
ACEH 1	Aceh Besar	228,919	Aceh Besar	373.755	53
	Banda Aceh City	122,210			
	Sabang City	22,626			
ACEH 2	Pidie	236,580	Pidie	327.769	46
	Pidie Jaya	91,189			
ACEH 3	Bireuen	236,549	Bireuen	236,549	33
ACEH 4	Aceh Tengah	123,222	Aceh Tengah	92267222	31
	Bener Meriah	92,144			
ACEH 5	Aceh Utara	313,355	Aceh Utara	410,982	58
	Lhokseumawe City	97,627			
ACEH 6	Aceh Timur	207,726	Aceh Timur	207,726	29
ACEH 7	Aceh Tamiang	158,181		251,770	36
	Langsa City	93,589			
ACEH 8	Aceh Tenggara	127,461	Aceh Tenggara	183,892	26
	Gayo Lues	56,431			
ACEH 9	Aceh Selatan	137,095	Aceh Selatan	294747	42
	Aceh Singkil	68,570			
	Aceh Barat Daya	89,082			
ACEH 10	Aceh Barat Daya	115,726	Aceh Barat Daya	324187	46
	Simeulue	50,369			
	Aceh Jaya	55,116			
	Nagan Raya	102,976			
TOTAL		2,826,743		2,826,743	400

Source: Aceh Independent Electoral Committee or KIP Aceh (2020) this research focuses on the voters of national and local political parties in Aceh province using explanatory and quantitative research. They empirically explain and estimate the influence between political communication, figures in political parties, government support, and political costs (price) on the intention to vote, which is mediated by public trust. This research was conducted within thirty days using google form for 60 days (2 months), namely from September to October 2021.

Data were collected using a questionnaire with a Likert scale consisting of five categories. Data were analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) using AMOS v22 software.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The condition of political parties in Aceh changed after the Aceh Tsunami, precisely in 2006 after the 2005 MOU agreement, one of which was the authority to form local parties and have Wali Nanggroe institutions. National Parties have long been active and side by side with the people in Aceh. The National Parties have continuously won elections, such as PPP and Golkar parties. Currently, the Aceh Party has won the election for three consecutive periods. However, the Aceh party's vote continues to decline, and the national party tends to increase, although not significantly. This research focuses on the uniqueness of the existence of local political parties in Aceh Province, which was initiated by discussions in the agreed Draft Law (RUU) regarding the Aceh Government, which began to be discussed in the center of the DPR on February 25 to July 5, 2006.

Figure 2: Research Model Results

A model is declared feasible if each of these indices has a cut of value as shown in Table 3 below:

Table 3: Goodness of Fit Indices

	Preferable Cut-off Value
χ^2 - chi-square	Expected small (under χ^2 table)
Significance Probability	≥ 0.05
RMSEA	Goodness of Fit Indices
GFI	≥ 0.90
AGFI	≥ 0.90
CMIN/DF	≤ 2.00
TLI	≥ 0.95
CFI	≥ 0.95

Source: Developed for this research

5. CONCLUSIONS

From the results of the research that has been done, several conclusions can be drawn, namely:

- 1) Political communication and government support for public trust. This means that the better political communication and government support, the more people's trust in political parties will increase.
- 2) Government support affects the intention to vote. This means that the higher the government's support for the party, the more people's intention to vote for politics will increase.
- 3) Public trust in the intention to vote. This means that the better public trust in political parties, the more people's intention to vote will increase.
- 4) Political communication affects the intention to vote through public trust. This means that the influence of political communication on voting intentions is mediated by public trust.
- 5) Government support affects the intention to vote through public trust. This means that the influence of government support on political intentions is mediated by public trust.

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References

- Abdussamad, Z. (2008). Challenges and prospects for Indonesian political communication in a welfare state. *Innovation Journal*.
- Abugre, J. B. (2017). Political Communication and Public Relations in the Ghanaian Media: Building an Emotional Environment with Propaganda. *Political Marketing and Management in Ghana*, 17–33. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-57373-1_2.
- Akbar, M. M., & Parvez, N. (2009). Impact of Service Quality, Trust, and Customer Satisfaction on Customers Loyalty. *ABAC Journal*, 29.
- Alfares, D. (2020). Political Communication of the Prosperous Justice Party (PKS) in the 2019 Legislative General Election in Purwakarta Regency. <http://elibrary.unikom.ac.id>.
- Almonds. (1999). Political Participation. <https://studylibid.com/doc/276778/participation-politik-almond>.
- Alwie, A. F. (2013). Political Marketing And The Decision To Choose Participants In The Regional Head Election In Urban And Suburban Groups (Study On Political Participants Groups In Pekanbaru City). *Journal of Socio-Economic Development*, 2(6), 220–243.
- Baskaran, T., & Hessami, Z. (2017). Political Alignment and Intergovernmental Transfers in Parliamentary Systems: Evidence from Germany. *Public Choice* 2017 171:1, 171(1), 75–98. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11127-016-0398-4>.
- Bela, H. S., & Utama, A. S. (2020). Motivasi Partisipasi Politik Perempuan Pada Pemilu Legislatif 2019 Di Kabupaten Ogan Komering Ulu. *Jurnal Pemerintahan Dan Politik*, 5(2). <https://doi.org/10.36982/JPG.V5I2.1029>.
- Bircan, Ç., & Saka, O. (2021). Lending Cycles and Real Outcomes: Costs of Political Misalignment. *The Economic Journal*, 131(639), 2763–2796.
- Bramulya Ikhsan, R., & Saggaff Shihab, M. (N.D.). Political Marketing Mix Dan Pengaruhnya Terhadap Keputusan Mahasiswa Universitas Lampung.
- Cacciatore, M. A., Meng, J., Boyd, B., & Reber, B. H. (2016). Political Ideology, MediaSource Preferences, and Messaging Strategies: A Global Perspective on Trust Building. *Public Relations Review*, 42(4), 616–626.
- Camaj, L. (2014). Media Use and Political Trust in an Emerging Democracy: Setting the Institutional Trust Agenda in Kosovo. *International Journal of Communication*, 8(0), 23. <https://ijoc.org/index.php/ijoc/article/view/2107>.
- Ceka, B. (2012). The Perils of Political Competition: Explaining Participation and Trust in Political Parties in Eastern Europe. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0010414012463908>, 46(12), 1610–1635. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0010414012463908>.
- Cangara, H. (2009). *Komunikasi Politik : Konsep, Teori, Dan Strategi*. 540. https://books.google.com/books/about/komunikasi_politik.
- Chaudhuri, A., & Holbrook, M. B. (2018). The Chain Of Effects From Brand Trust And Brand Affect To Brand Performance: The Role Of Brand Loyalty.
- Cheborgei, W. C., & Kamaara, M. (2017). Strategic Journals Influence Of Personal Branding On Organizational Performance In The Affluent Banking Industry In Kenya.
- Clara. (2013). the Legitimacy of Democracy and Trust in the Political Institutions in the Czech Republic on JSTOR. Clara. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/41133170>.

- Corral Margarita. (2008). (Mis) Trust In Political Parties in Latin America. Vanderbilt University, Vol .2, 1–6.
- Dann, S., & Hughes, A. (2016). Lessons From Kevin 07 TM : Political Marketing ECommerce View Project Selfie View Project. <https://doi.org/10.2104/Mbr08010>.
- Darc, J., Manik, N., & Hum*, M. (2013). Kekuasaan Dan Kepemimpinan Sebagai Proses Sosial Dalam Bermasyarakat. *Society*, 1(1), 130355.
- Fishbein, Martin dan Icek Ajzen. 2010. Predicting and Changing Behavior: The Reasoned Action Approach. New York: Psychology Press.
- Lees-Marshment, J. 2005, the marketing campaign: the British general election of 2005, *Journal of Marketing Management*, 21 (9/10), 1151-60.
- Muhammad Fuad Othman Assessment of Political Participation and Democratic Governance in Nigeria's Fourth Republic DOI:10.47836/pjssh.29.1.30.
- Oladipupo Abdullahi Akinola, Bahiyah Omar and Lambe Kayode Mustapha. Saliency in the Media and Political Trust in Nigeria: The Mediating Role of Political Participation. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47836/pjssh.29.4.03>.
- Warneryd, Karl Erik. 1999. *The Psychology of Saving: A Study on Economic Psychology*. Stockholm: Edward Elgar Publishing.